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Discursive- Material Struggles over Legitimate Heroism A Visual Essay on Floating Signifiers and Their Materiality in the Estonian Second World War Memorialscape

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Through a combination of historical research and a series of research visits, this visual essay reflects on how Estonian memorials, related to the Second World War; are discursive-material assemblages, that function as floating signifiers. Grounded in a post-structuralist theorization of contingency, overdetermination and discursive struggle – particularly inspired by Laclau and Mouffe's (1985) work – the notion of floating signifiers captures the signifiatory diversity of key concepts which have become integrated in different (and competing) discourses. By extending this framework to recent theoretical expansions that aim to validate both the discursive and the material (Carpentier, 2017), also the floating of discursive-material memorial assemblages can be incorporated into this analysis.

This article, in particular, focusses on the discursive-material struggles over the articulation of the Estonian Second World War hero in the Estonian memorialscape, at a time when the Estonian government has been removing a considerable number of Soviet memorials from the Estonian public space (and plans to remove more). Beginning with the argument that not every Estonian Second World War memorial has been subjected to this discursive-material struggle, we then analyse the discursive-material struggle over the Soviet hero and the Waffen-SS hero, together with the remarkable absence of memorializations of the independent Estonian (nationalist) hero. In a case study, we zoom in on how a prestigious military decoration, the Cross of Liberty, becomes a significant illustration of the workings of the floating signifier, playing a role in both mainstream and radical-right-wing discourses about the Estonian hero during the Second World War. In our conclusion, we reflect about the absence of closure on what is the past, present and future of Estonia, and the ethical concerns that this absence raises.

Keywords: memorialscape, floating signifier, discursive-material memorial assemblage, Estonia, Nazi Germany, USSR, heroism, memorialization

Introduction

The 2022 Russian escalation of the Russo-Ukrainian War, with its invasion of large parts of Ukraine, had many consequences, in many places of the world, with many different levels of intensity. In Estonia, a country with a substantial Russian-speaking minority, this escalation led – among others – to another government intervention in the Estonian memorialscape (Carr 2012), with the removal of a considerable number of Soviet memorials (and plans to remove more) from the Estonian public space. Especially symbolic and significant was the removal of a Soviet T-34/85 memorial tank from Narva, a city on the border with Russia with a majority of Russian-speaking Estonians. This memorial commemorated the crossing of the Narva river by Soviet Red Army troops in 1944. On 16 August 2022, the tank was lifted on a military truck, and driven to the Estonian War Museum, close to Tallinn, the Estonian capital (Estonian War Museum 2022; Wright 2022).

Many different analyses of this material, but also deeply discursive and performative interventions, are possible in the Estonian memorialscape. In this article we want to reflect on how the memorials related to the Second World War are discursive-material assemblages, that function as floating signifiers. Through a combination of historical research with a series of research visits to key Estonian memorials in November 2022 and January 2023 – some of them already removed, others untouched – we analyze how these memorials are sometimes beyond the discursive struggles over the history of the Second World War and Estonian identity, while in other cases, they are at the very center of these discursive struggles. As our analysis will show, one of the key components of this discursive struggle is related to the entitlement to the discursive position of the hero, which is fiercely contested. At the same time, we also want to argue that there is no closure to this discursive struggle, even though the removal of many of the Soviet memorials is a major attempt to stop the floating of these signifiers, and to establish a particular hegemony of legitimate heroism.

Before moving to the theoretical discussion on the floating signifier, it is important to stress that this article is a visual essay, which means that it makes extensive use of photography,¹ which is the defining element of the visual essay (Grady, 1991; 1996). Still, a significant portion of the article uses

¹ All photographs are by Nico Carpentier.

written text, to provide the contextualization deemed necessary. Vital for the genre of the visual essay is that the photographic components do not serve as mere illustrations of the academic analysis, but benefit from the same level of importance as the written text, with both contributing equally to the strength of this analysis. This is also why the written text does not provide an immediate *explanation* of each photograph, and why the photographs have titles, and not descriptions. At the same time, the analysis is still grounded in qualitative methodology, selecting memorials through theoretical sampling, and performing a discourse-material analysis (Carpentier 2017) on the observations and their photographic representations.

What is a Floating Signifier?

In post-structuralist theory, one of the key ideas is the contingency of social reality, arguing that any ultimate fixation is lacking, even though political processes incessantly (attempt to) fixate social reality. Contingency does not imply the total fluidity of everything combined with everything all the time, though; after all, “a discourse incapable of generating any fixity of meaning is the discourse of the psychotic” (Laclau and Mouffe 1985, 112). In contrast, contingency refers to the impossibility of reaching “a final closure” (Howarth 1998, 273), or, in other words, to the always-present possibility of change. One other concept that has frequently been used to clarify the impossibility of ultimate fixation is overdetermination, which allows to move away from the idea that society is determined by a particular force (e.g., class). Laclau and Mouffe (1985) borrowed the originally Freudian concept of overdetermination from Althusser (1982), though not without altering its meaning. They saw identity as a fusion of a multiplicity of identities, where the overdetermined presence of some identities in others prevents their closure:

For it, the sense of every identity is overdetermined inasmuch as all literality appears as constitutively subverted and exceeded; far from there being an essentialist totalization, or a no less essentialist separation among objects, the presence of some objects in the others prevents any of their identities from being fixed. (Laclau and Mouffe 1985, 104)

In discourse theory, contingency (and overdetermination) are situated on both the intradiscursive and the interdiscursive level. Discourses themselves are liable to change through the logics of articulation and de-articulation.

Contingency at the intradiscursive level means that a discourse can change, because elements are added to it or removed from it, a process which affects the entire discourse. Contingency also arises at the interdiscursive level, because discourses engage with each other in discursive struggles over hegemony. In some cases, a particular discourse manages to victoriously establish this hegemony, thus becoming a social imaginary or horizon, but in many other cases these discursive struggles remain ongoing, with discourses trying to establish chains of equivalence that would consolidate their position as hegemonic, but simultaneously being countered by other discourses that attempt to do the same, resulting in a restless power play, without any discourse achieving its ultimate objective of establishing hegemony.

Which brings us to the concept of the floating signifier. Discourses, in their attempts to establish chains of equivalences, aim to integrate particular signifiers, thus establishing and enlarging their discursive alliances. Almost unavoidably, different discourses (attempt to) integrate the same signifiers, and – as the practice of articulation (into a discourse) renders meaning specific – these *popular* signifiers assume different meanings in different contexts/discourses, enhancing contingency once again. In discourse theory, signifiers that become integrated into different discourses and that thus obtain different meanings, are labelled floating signifiers. They are signifiers that are “overflowed with meaning” (Torfing 1999, 301), or, in Laclau’s words, their meaning is “indeterminate between alternative equivalential frontiers” (2005, 131). In dealing with the “structural pressure of *rival* hegemonic projects,” (131, emphasis in original) they move beyond discursive frontiers, and the concept of the floating signifier allows us to “apprehend the logic of displacements of that frontier” (133). Still, this does not mean that there is total fluidity, because each discourse that articulates a floating signifier partially fixates its meaning. In some cases, as we will see, particular political interventions can limit the range of floating (without completely arresting this floating). And, moreover, “a purely psychotic universe, where we would have a pure floating without any partial fixation, is not thinkable either” (Laclau 2005, 133).

Many concepts have been analyzed as floating signifiers,² including concepts as diverse as participation (Carpentier 2017), security (Makarychev 2012), race and ethnicity (Hall 1997; Best and Byrd 2015), nature (Conesa-Sevilla

2 In some cases, these articles focus more on the empty signifier than the floating signifier, but a discussion on the differences between these – overlapping – concepts is beyond the scope of this article.

2018), celebrity (Coombe 1992), migrant, refugee, and diaspora (Tošić 2022), trafficking (Davida 2015), fake news (Farkas and Schou 2018), and, more relevant in the context of this article, trauma and victimhood (van den Berg 2016), the enemy (Carpentier 2011) and the hero (Bale 2006).

In some cases, also more material objects have been marked as floating signifiers, with, for instance, face masks (Van Gorp 2021) and photographs (Tomanić-Trivundža and Vezovnik 2021). People have also been analyzed from this perspective, with, for instance, Curtis and Curtis' (2001, 259) analysis of Jack the Ripper. These more material-focused research projects bring out highly relevant questions about the status of the floating signifier – which is a discourse-theoretical concept – in relation to materiality. If we want to take the premise of discursive-material entanglement (Carpentier 2017) seriously, we should acknowledge that signifiers always have their material condensations, and that they together form discursive-material assemblages. As the components of these discursive-material assemblages are inseparable, we can make the argument that these assemblages themselves can also float, receiving different meanings in different discourses, and that in other cases, these assemblages can contribute to the strengthening of (broader) discourses. In turn, these discourses engage in discursive struggles with each other, and they all might attempt to (re-)signify discursive-material assemblages, turning them into floating signifiers once again.

What is important here is that these material condensations do not necessarily have to be linguistic; as the previously mentioned research shows, discursive-material assemblages with objects and people can also become floating signifiers, with the meaning allocated to them integrated into different competing discourses. This brings us to the logic of memorialization, as also discursive-material memorial assemblages can, in part or as a whole, function as floating signifiers.

The Context: Second World War Memorials in Estonia

There are many different types of memorials, but in this visual essay we want to focus on the war memorials in Estonia, particularly (but not completely exclusively) on those related to the Second World War. In cases where the visual research project produced relevant examples outside this period, which, for instance, illustrates the dynamics of memorialization of the Second World

War, these examples were still included. Our analysis, based on field work in Estonia in November 2022 and January 2023, aims to demonstrate the workings of floating signifiers in the Estonian memorialscape, in a period of strategic attempts to intervene and re-signify the discursive construction of Estonia's history through a series of material alterations.

Estonia's relationship with the Second World War is complicated, as the small nation in the Baltic, after the country declared its independence in 1918, was confronted with two occupying forces taking turns. Between 1918 and 1920, the country fought its War of Independence with the Soviet Union – and at some point, with (Baltic) German forces – and had its independence recognized by the Soviet Union on 2 February 1920 with the Treaty of Tartu. Then, as the August 1939 German-Soviet Nonaggression Pact, with its secret supplementary protocol, had placed Estonia in the Soviet sphere of influence, the Soviet Union effectively took control of the country in mid-June 1940 (North 2015, 255–256), swiftly implementing “the forced collectivization of agriculture and increased peasant production quotas” (North 2015, 256). The Stalinist terror that followed, accumulated in the deportation of thousands of Estonian families, especially during the 14 June 1941 mass deportation (North 2015, 256; see also Plakans 2011, 347).

When Nazi Germany attacked the Soviet Union in June of 1941, the Baltic states were also conquered. During the fighting, “large numbers of civilians seized the opportunity to form guerilla [sic] units that engaged the Soviet forces as best they could,” resulting in the 5000 strong Estonian guerrilla force killing around 500 Soviet soldiers (Plakans 2011, 348). After the conquest by Nazi Germany, the guerrilla forces were quickly disarmed, and Estonia became part of *Ostland*, an administrative region with comprised of the three Baltic states and part of Byelorussia. While originally around 12000 Estonians were active in “so-called ‘volunteer police battalions,’ serving mostly within the borders of each country” (Plakans 2011, 356), Nazi Germany established the Estonian Legion in 1942, which was transformed in the 3rd Estonian SS Volunteer Brigade in May of 1943. Originally, this unit had around 5000 soldiers.³ Still, recruitment campaigns often only had limited success, and mobilization was a frequently used alternative (Kaasik 2011).

The Nazi occupation also set the stage for the Holocaust in this region, with the murder of all people considered *undesirable*, including Jewish people,

3 Others (voluntarily) joined the Finnish army, to fight against the Soviet Union (North 2015, 258).

Roma, people with mental illnesses, and communists. There were only a few thousand Jews in Estonia, and those who remained in the country stood little chance. The genocide was extremely swift and thorough: On 20 January 1942 already, the Nazi regime declared Estonia to be *judenfrei*, or ethnically cleansed (Katz 2012, 3).

Eventually, the Soviet Union pushed back the Nazi-German forces and retook control of Estonia in 1944, despite strong Estonian (and German) resistance. In January 1944, the Estonian SS Brigade was transformed into the 20th Estonian SS Volunteer Division⁴ and strengthened by some of the more than 30000 Estonians (Hiio 2006, 942) who responded to the call of the Estonian pre-war prime minister, Jüri Uluots, to take up arms to prevent another Soviet occupation. A considerable number of Estonians – Plakans (2011, 357) estimates their number to also be at 30000 – fought with communist Partisans and the Red Army. Nevertheless, by September 1944, Estonia found itself under Soviet control again (North 2015, 258), even though armed resistance – by the so-called Forest Brothers – continued until the mid-1950s (Plakans 2011, 362; see also Laar 1992). Only in 1991 was Estonian independence was restored.

This complicated and traumatizing history has produced a significant number of memorials in Estonia, which have continued to be the object of a series of discursive struggles, and even material resistance in some cases. This is not a recent phenomenon, as, for instance, “The graves of those who fell on the other side did not deserve to be preserved in the eyes of the Soviets. In 1945 already, the authorities ordered to liquidate the graves of those who fought on the German side” (Kraft 2013, 202; our translation). When we look at the 21st century, we can find an example of this discursive-material struggle, when one monument in Tallinn, the so-called Bronze Soldier, was moved from the city center to a cemetery in the outskirts. This monument was erected in 1947 in the town’s center, as the Monument to the Liberators of Tallinn, which was once the burial place of 13 Soviet soldiers (Wilson 2015, 170). In April 2007, this monument was moved to Tallinn’s outskirts, becoming confined to the Tallinn Defence Forces Cemetery (see Bruggemann and Kasekamp 2008; Lehti, et al. 2008; Smith 2008; Melchior and Visser 2011; Wilson 2015; Bellentani

4 In May 1944, the Division was renamed again and became the 20th Waffen Grenadier Division of the SS (1st Estonian).

2021; Kazharski and Makarychev 2022).⁵ This removal triggered a strong response, leading some authors, for example Smith (2008) to label this a War of Monuments. On the first evening of the protest, which lasted for two nights, protesters “headed into central Tallinn where cars were set ablaze, windows smashed and shops looted. One young man, a Russian citizen, involved in the looting was stabbed to death” (Bruggemann and Kasekamp 2008: 436).

With the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine, and the decision of the Estonian government to remove a series of Soviet memorials, another less violent phase of this discursive-material struggle was initiated. A Government Office’s Soviet Monuments Working Group was established (State Chancellery 2022), but the Estonian government did not wait for its results (which came in November 2022). In August already, the Estonian government decided to remove a first series of memorials (especially in the city of Narva), legitimated by the need to protect public order (Republic of Estonia Government 2022). In a report published on 23 November 2022, the working group then evaluated 322 memorials, and advised that 244 would be removed or replaced. At the time the report was published, 56 memorials had already been removed (Turovski 2022).

Beyond the Floating

Within this context of contestation, it is important to stress that not all memorials have been engulfed in these discursive struggles, which also prevents these discursive-material memorial assemblages from becoming floating signifiers. Sometimes these memorials become exempt because their semi-sacred nature shifts them beyond contestation, while in other cases their perceived insignificance protects them. An example of the former is related to the protective status that child-victims benefit from, as the discourse of innocence – a vital component of the construction of childhood, especially in the Western world (Garlen 2020, 968) – places these assemblages beyond (most) possible re-articulations that would undermine or jeopardize the existence of these memorials, for instance, by defining those children as perpetrators, criminals, or simply as evil. In the latter case, the invisibility of some memorials also provides them with protection, as they become excluded from incorporation in any discursive-material assemblage, and they are often

⁵ See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/t-0860>.

left to decay. Here, no discourse expresses any interest in articulation, which also excludes these discursive-material assemblages from floating.

One example of a memorial that is (almost) beyond contestation is situated in the Alevi cemetery in the Estonian coastal town of Pärnu in the small Jewish section. The memorial consists of a commemorative stone for 34 Jewish children that were killed on 2 November 1941.⁶ The commemorative stone, placed in 2009 (Peegel 2009), refers to the last phase of the extermination of the Jewish community in Pärnu, the fourth largest Jewish community in Estonia. The Jewish people who did not manage to flee the city were imprisoned in the Bett's Warehouse⁷ camp, which was administered by the local *Omakaitse* (Home Guard). In the first phase, most Jewish men in Pärnu were killed in July and August 1941, by firing squad in the nearby forests. Most Jewish women and children were killed later, in October and November 1941, with most children killed in the local synagogue (Maripuu 2006, 655).

A second example is also located in Pärnu, at one of the 1941 execution sites in the Reiu forest, close to the seaside. The entry of the German army in Pärnu on 8 July 1941 also meant that – apart from the 137 Jewish people killed in Pärnu (Maripuu 2006, 655; Kraft 2013, 216) – many hundreds more lost their lives. Maripuu (2006, 655) mentions a total of 494 people who were shot in Pärnu from 12 July to 12 December 1941. He adds that

a special commando consisting of 30 men [...] had been formed in Pärnu for carrying out the death sentences issued by political police. It had also been established that most of the executions were carried out by the commando mentioned above, not by the Germans. (Maripuu 2006, 654–655)

The Reiu forest memorial⁸ has two elements, from different eras. The first element is an obelisk from 1967, with one remaining plaque (the second one has disappeared), with the following text: “Seven hundred Soviet citizens were massacred here by the fascists in 1941–1944.” The second element, added

6 The 34 children's names are at the back of the commemorative stone and all of them are featured on the list of Jewish Holocaust victims in Estonia at <https://eesti-malu-instituut.github.io/dtable/?lang=en&data=jews>.

7 For the history of the warehouse see <https://parnu.postimees.ee/2335181/parnu-tana-ulejoe-linatoostus-ja-beti-ait>.

8 See more at: <https://militaryheritagetourism.info/en/military/sites/view/477>. The Government Office's Soviet Monuments Working Group (2022, 128) listed this memorial in its report, but considered it a “neutral grave marker.”

**2.novembril 1941 Juudi palvemajas
Pärnus tapeti 34 last ainult
sellepärast, et nad olid juudid.**

**On November 2, 1941 34 children
were killed in the Jewish pray house in
Pärnu just because they were Jews.**

**United States Commission for
The Preservation of America's Heritage Abroad
Holocaust Education Trust
National Fund of the Republic of Austria for
Victims of National Socialism**

Figure 1. 34 Children and Teddy Bears.

Figure 2. *Plastic Toy Empathy.*

nearby after the 1991 re-establishment of the Republic of Estonia,⁹ has the shape of a tombstone, with this text in Estonian and Russian: “Here innocent children were executed.”

Both memorials are related to the period of Nazi occupation, and the 1941 killings of Estonians, including the annihilation of the remaining Estonian-Jewish community in Pärnu. Both memorials are, either entirely or partially, focused on children, invoking the discourse that constructs children as innocent. The memorials demonstrate the remembrance of the dead, and facilitate the mourning of the survivors and others affected. The additions of toys, in both cases, shows that those living now also express their empathy.

Nevertheless, war memorials remain deeply political, as is also the case here. The Soviet era monument in Reiu does not mention Jewish people, only “Soviet citizens,” which aligns with the Soviet narrative of the Great Patriotic War, as “the foundational mythology for the legitimate expansion of the Soviet Union” (Kattago 2008, 435), which did not provide (much) space for the specificity of the Holocaust (Tumarkin 2003; Zeltser 2018). Moreover, the more recent addition to the Reiu monument refers to *children* in general terms, and not to the Holocaust itself. For that explicit reference, we need to go to the memorial at the Jewish section of the Alevi cemetery. It is important to add here that, even though the Estonian government has made headway in recognizing the Holocaust, “Estonia was late to acknowledge and engage with its role in the Holocaust” (Jin 2019).

An example of the invisibility of memorials (as memorials) is Bett’s Warehouse (*Beti Ladu*, *Beti Linaait*, or *Beti Ait* in Estonian), the prison camp we mentioned earlier. In this camp, the Jewish women and children of Pärnu were imprisoned (among others) before they were killed. The building is situated close to the Sauga river, a sidearm of the Pärnu river, in a more industrial part of the city. It is in an advanced state of decay, with the masonry and brickwork disintegrating in many parts of the building, and some windows bricked up. Still, other parts of the building have been repaired, and appear to still be in use. An expert assessment, part of a project on mapping 20th century architecture, contains a series of photographs which demonstrate that some of the warehouse’s rooms have indeed been renovated (Hansen 2011, 15–17). This report pleads for the building to be protected, because of its

⁹ See more at: <https://militaryheritagetourism.info/en/military/sites/view/477>.

“architectural, historical, and typological value,” also arguing that “during the whirlwind of the events of the Second World War, [the warehouse] acquired a notorious reputation in Pärnu as the place where the Holocaust was carried out, the burden of which this building will carry with it until the end of its life” (Hansen 2011, 7; our translation).

Despite the building’s significance, there is no commemorative plaque on the building, or any other material reference to the building’s tragic history. Interestingly, the expert assessment report mentions that there used to be a plaque: “On October 20, 1970, a commemorative plaque was installed on the building in memory of the people who died in the Holocaust” (Hansen 2011, 4; our translation), but currently no plaque is present. Also the building’s ownership, currently in the hands of a company called Rivest OÜ,¹⁰ seems unstable, as on several occasions, for instance in 2018 and in 2022, the building has been included in the catalogue of real estate agents (including Domus, K.V.EE and LVM) who were trying to sell it. The building’s low-visibility status was confirmed during our January 2023 site visit, when we inquired in the nearby Koidula museum about the warehouse-camp’s existence. Even though the museum is only 250 meters from the warehouse, the person at the desk of the museum had no knowledge of it.

After the Floating: Denying the Hero Signifier to the Soviet Soldiers

One of the main floating signifiers in relation to war is the hero, as the discourse on self and enemy of both belligerent parties articulate different people and actions/events as (legitimate) heroes and heroic. As a consequence, the signifier hero receives different (material) loads, and starts to slide. In the Estonian case, during and after the Second World War, the hero can refer to the Soviet hero, who fought for the socialist cause, which implied the creation of a classless society but also the integration of Estonia in the USSR. The hero could also refer to the Waffen-SS hero, who fought with the Nazi-German army against the Red army in order to *purify* the Baltic region from elements they considered strange. Or it could also refer to the nationalist-Estonian hero who fought for Estonian independence, possibly in alliance with other regimes, for instrumentalist motives, without necessarily identifying with their ideological projects.

10 See more at: <https://www.teatmik.ee/en/landregpart/56405>.

Figure 3. *Neglecting the Holocaust Assemblage.*

Figure 4. *Warehouse in Decay.*

Even if different articulations of the hero coexisted, particular articulations were hegemonic in particular periods, depending on which regime controlled the Estonian territory. As these regime changes occurred frequently during the Second World War, the dominant articulations of the legitimate hero also changed, as did their memorialization. One example is the Maarjamäe memorial complex, which was originally the 1940 reburial site of Soviet sailors executed in 1919 in the Naissaar camp (Minnik 2014, 105; Hiio 2021, 186–187). In 1941, after the German army captured Tallinn, Maarjamäe became the burial site for German soldiers (and around 100 Estonians), but when the Soviets retook control in 1944, the German cemetery was levelled (Bellentani 2021, 119), and it became a Soviet burial site once again (Hiio 2021, 181). On 30 July 1960, a large obelisk, designed by architect Mart Port and sculptor Lembit Tolli (Estonian Centre for Architecture 2020, see also Martínez 2022, 69) was unveiled, to commemorate the evacuation of the Baltic Fleet from Tallinn to Helsinki and Kronstadt in 1918. Later, in 1975, stage one of the memorial complex, designed by architect Allan Murdmaa and sculptor Matti Varik,¹¹ was opened, with stage two never (entirely) completed (Hiio 2021, 222). After the Estonian independence, the German soldiers buried at this location became more visible again, with crosses and memorial stones added to the site.¹² Later, in 2018, the large Memorial to the Victims of Communism¹³ was constructed, next to the Soviet memorial complex. The new memorial, by Kalle Vellevoog, Jaan Tiidemann and Tiiu Truus, with sculptor Kirke Kangro, opened on 23 August 2018 (Hiio 2021, 182).

In the 21st century, with the Soviet memorials being removed, the Soviet hero lost even more of its visibility in Estonian society, further limiting the ability in which the hero signifier could float, but without completely halting the floating. One key element – which has already been mentioned above – was the removal of the Bronze Soldier monument in April 2007 from its original location in Tallinn, and its relocation at the Defence Forces cemetery.

August 2022 was the start of a new wave of removals of Soviet memorials, with the removal of the T-34/85 tank memorial on 16 August 2022 and the transfer of the tank to the Estonian War Museum in Viimsi, near Tallinn (White 2022), as the most emblematic instance, to which we referred in our introduction. The

11 See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/t-0620>; <https://www.visitestonia.com/en/maarjamae-memorial>.

12 See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/t-0650>.

13 See more at: <https://www.memoriaal.ee/en/memorial/>.

Figure 5. *Cemetery as a Double Confinement.*

large base of the T-34/85 memorial, constructed in 1970,¹⁴ just a few meters from the river that is now the border with Russia, included the following text in Estonian and Russian: “On 25–26 June 1944, the Leningrad front advanced into this region of the Narva River, broke through the fascist German defense and liberated the city of Narva” (Kattago 2008, 437).

But a whole series of other memorials were removed in Narva, including the memorial for Soviet junior lieutenant Igor Grafov, who was killed on the river bank after his unit established a bridgehead there. The memorial, celebrating this Hero of the Soviet Union, was inaugurated in 1973, 50 years after his birthdate.¹⁵ Moreover, Igor Grafov also had a street named after him in 1966,¹⁶ with one of the houses in this street being adorned with a commemorative plaque, briefly explaining Grafov’s actions in Estonian and Russian. Next to the street name plate, metal flag holders have been attached to the wall, no longer in use. The commemorative plaque is described by the Government Office’s Soviet Monuments Working Group (2022, 169) as a “red monument”,

¹⁴ See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/iv-1010>.

¹⁵ See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/iv-1020>.

¹⁶ See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/iv-1020>.

which “must be removed from public space.” In October 2022, the Place Names Board of Estonia asked the National Archives of Estonia for advice on seven Red army soldiers who had streets named after them, including Igor Grafov. The report of the National Archives, released at the end of November 2022 deemed these street names “inappropriate and incompatible with contemporary understandings of Estonian history and culture” (Kook 2022).

The 2022 interventions in the Estonian memorialscape did not go unnoticed, even though the violence that accompanied the 2007 displacement of the Tallinn Bronze Soldier statue did not occur. In particular in Narva, with its many Russian-speaking Estonians, the sense of mourning was made palpable through the decoration of the sites from which memorials were removed. Here, Kattago (2008), writing about the period where the Narva Soviet memorials were still intact, makes two important points. Firstly, the Soviet memorials are a significant part of the identity constructions of the Russian-speaking Estonians (Kattago 2008, 436), providing them with identity markers to claim their specificity (and rights). Secondly, especially the T-34/85 tank memorial – even when it was located outside the city center – was very much part of the everyday life of the Narva community: “It serves as a commemorative place for the glorification of the Red Army, a place for newlyweds to tie their ribbons around their gun and a place for honoring military death” (Kattago 2008, 438, see also Nikolajev 2022).

The response to this loss was significant. After its removal, the location of T-34/85 tank memorial, with the river demarcating the border with Russia behind it, was covered with a large heart-shaped collection of candles and flowers. After the removal of the Grafov memorial, it received the same treatment, with, in this case, a laminated photograph of how the memorial used to look, placed among the flowers and candles.

The interventions of the Estonian government, guided by the Soviet Monuments Working Group not only removed memorials that were deemed inappropriate, but replaced many of these memorials with a uniform marker: A small black stone with the text “Victims of World War II” engraved in white letters in Estonian, as is, for instance, the case at the Kirbla cemetery.¹⁷ The combination of the strategy of removal, disconnecting the Soviet hero signifier

17 See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/pa-0300>. Later, in January 2023, newly designed markers (designed by Kirke Kangro) were placed with the same text (Cole 2023).

Figure 6. *One Marker of the Border with Russia Left.*

Figure 7. *Tank Affection.*

Figure 8. *The T-34/85's New Home.*

Figure 9. *For Ever and Ever a Hero of the Soviet Union.*

Figure 10. *What Once Was.*

Figure 11. *No more Flags for Igor Grafov.*

Figure 12. *From Heroes to Uniformized Victims.*

from the memorial, with the strategies of uniformization and neutralization, through similar superimpositions of the victim signifier, re-signifies the memorial and again reduces the capacity of the hero signifier to float.

The Struggle Over the Waffen-SS Hero

But the Soviet hero was not the only group articulated as a hero. Also the Waffen-SS soldiers, in their fight against the USSR, became elevated to the status of hero, especially in particular moments in time. Here too, the hero signifier is contested, as the articulation of Estonians with the Nazi war assemblage poses a multitude of ethical issues for many Estonians, while more radical-nationalist actors celebrate this alliance. Even the attempted rearticulation of this alliance, mediated through the discourse of instrumentalization, where Estonians are positioned as using Nazi Germany to prevent a greater evil – namely a Soviet victory and the Soviet re-taking of Estonia – remains deeply contested. Still, Estonian radical-right-wing actors use memorials (among others) to protect the articulation of the Estonian Waffen-SS soldier as a legitimate hero.

One particularly important place is the Old park (and the adjacent Victory park) in Pärnu, which is itself a microcosmos of the discursive-material struggle over the Second World War memorials, which legitimates a more detailed description. Currently, only one of the memorials is left standing. Before, at different times, several memorials used to be placed in this park. In 1940, a temporary memorial for the 1905 and 1917 uprisings and the 1924 communist coup was built in the park, already acting as a burial site (Kraft 2013, 209; 213). When the German army took control of Pärnu, that memorial was burned. After the Soviet regime retook control, the park became a burial site for the (Soviet) casualties of the Nazis, with a temporary marker again, this time referring to (only) 1905, 1917, and 1941 (Kraft 2013, 223). A more permanent memorial, by the sculptor Juhan Raudsepp, was inaugurated on 9 May 1958 (Kraft 2013, 223).¹⁸ This memorial mentioned 1905, 1917, 1924 and 1941-1944, conveniently ignoring “the years when Stalin and Hitler were allied, namely 1939–1941,” as was Soviet custom (Kattago 2008, 443). In August 2022, this Soviet memorial was removed from the park. The bodies in the mass grave were exhumed (Vilgats 2022) and transferred to Uulu cemetery, 15 km south of Pärnu.

But importantly, in 2002, another memorial was erected in the park. What is now called the Lihula memorial, featured a man in an Estonian SS uniform, holding a German sub-machine gun (*BBC News* 2002), with one of the insignia used by the 20th Waffen Grenadier Division of the SS (1st Estonian) on his collar. The collar patch has the letter E, with a hand holding a sword, a symbol which was taken from the most prestigious Estonian medal from the War of Independence period, the Cross of Liberty.¹⁹ The inscription on the memorial originally read: “To all Estonian soldiers who died for their homeland and free Europe in the Second War of Independence 1940-1945.”²⁰ Following this intense critique – including the one formulated by the then Estonian prime minister, Siim Kallas – the memorial was removed after only nine days, based on a decision made by the city government.

After the Lihula memorial was removed from the Victory Park in Pärnu, the mayor of Lihula, Tiit Madisson, welcomed the memorial in his town,

18 See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/pa-1010>.

19 There were also other variations of the collar patches, see below (Williamson, 2004: 37; Taylor, 1986: 207–216).

20 “Kõigile Eesti sõduritele, kes II vabadussõjas langesid kodumaa ja vaba Euroopa eest 1940-1945” (*BBC News* 2002).

where it was unveiled on 20 August 2004 (*BBC News* 2004). Interestingly, the text has since been changed, and it now read(s): “To the Estonian men who fought against Bolshevism in 1940-1945 and for the restoration of Estonian independence.” The Estonian government opposed this re-installation and on 2 September 2004, the memorial was forcibly removed, requiring the intervention of the Estonian riot police (Gunter 2004).²¹ Later, on 15 October 2005, the Lihula memorial found its place in Lagedi (near Tallinn), on the premises of the privately owned Museum of the Fight for Estonia’s Freedom.²² But its former location, at one of the Lihula cemeteries (the *old cemetery*), is also a tangible place of loss, with the base of the memorial still visible, and a large ornamental vase placed on top of it. Behind it, we can find an explanatory panel, documenting both the placement of the memorial and its replacement. Most importantly, we can also find here the grave of Tiit Madisson, the former mayor of Lihula, who was instrumental in the placement of the memorial there, next to the memorial’s former location. He died on 21 June 2021 (Lääneranna Municipal Council and Government 2021).

The Almost Invisible Estonian Heroes of the Second World War

Interestingly, the third possible articulation of the hero, the independent Estonian hero – not connected to other regimes – only has a weak presence in the Estonian memorialscape that is related to the Second World War.²³ Of course, there are numerous memorials to celebrate Estonian independence, and the heroes of 1918–1920. But the articulation of the independent Estonian hero is remarkably absent from the Second World War period, which leaves the hero signifier floating between Soviet and Waffen-SS hero articulations.

However, there are a few exceptions.²⁴ One example is the Memorial of the Battle of Raua street, which took place a few days after Estonia had surrendered to the Soviet occupation. It is a small memorial, encroached by everyday (school) life. The text on the memorial reads: “Here, on 21 June 1940, the armed counterattack of the communications battalion against the Soviet

21 In 2018, the Estonian Conservative People’s Party (EKRE) placed a replica of the memorial in Lihula, arguing for the return of the original to this location (Whyte 2018).

22 See more at: <http://vabadusvoitlus.ee/sundmused/>.

23 The so-called Forest Brothers, an anti-Soviet guerrilla movement, is an important addition. As they were mostly active after the Second World War, they are not included here.

24 Of course, as the Reiu forest memorial illustrates, Estonian heroes were acknowledged in the Soviet memorials, but they were articulated as Soviet citizens at the time.

Figure 13. Tiit Madisson's Grave.

Figure 14. The Waffen-SS Soldier that Does not Leave.

Figure 15. *Studying by the Resistance to the Soviet-Takeover.*

Figure 16. *The Multiple Tragedies of the Anti-Tank Ditch.*

occupation took place.” This skirmish in (and around) the school building was the only significant resistance of the Estonian military against the Soviet occupation. As can be read at the database entry of the war museums of Estonia: the two killed Estonian soldiers “were among the few Estonian soldiers who died during World War II in Estonian uniform and under the Estonian flag.”²⁵ The building is currently still a school, and together with the ongoing roadworks, the memorial stone is a bit lost in the movements of everyday life, even though ceremonies still take place here once in a while.

Another more complex example is the Jalaka Line Memorial in Lemmatsi, close to Tartu. The 16-meter-long memorial wall, by sculptor Elmar Rebane and architect Väino Tamm, was completed in 1964, as the “Memorial to the Victims of Fascism” (Matvei 2011), while it is now more often referred to as the “Jalaka Line Memorial.”²⁶ The site is not only a memorial for a Nazi execution site – currently engulfed by business buildings, with the construction company behind the memorial flying the flag of the Federal Republic of Germany – but it also commemorates the Soviet-enforced labor of the citizens of Tartu, who had to build a large anti-tank ditch, which was supposed to prevent the Nazi-German army from taking the city of Tartu. The Government Office’s Soviet Monuments Working Group (2022, 239) considered the Jalaka Line Memorial “a neutral memorial.” This conclusion is understandable, as the memorial wisely aggregates different articulations, also paying attention to Estonian civil heroism (and suffering), and thus itself becoming a floating discursive-material assemblage.

A Floating Signifier: The Cross of Liberty

The Cross of Liberty is a prestigious Estonian military decoration, which was established on 24 February 1919, during the 1918–1920 Estonian War of Independence, the first anniversary of the proclamation of independence in Tallinn. Even though the decoration was never officially revoked, the bestowal of the decoration was ended (by law) on 19 June 1925. The decoration has three divisions, awarded for military merits, personal courage/bravery/valor and administrative and civilian services, which each had three classes (I to

²⁵ See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/t-0750>.

²⁶ See more at: <https://militaryheritagetourism.info/en/military/sites/view/261?2>; <https://register.muinasa.ee/public.php?menuID=photolibrary&action=view&id=15736>.

III).²⁷ Walter (1998, 261) provides some of the basic statistics about the Cross of Liberty:

All in all 3215 Crosses of Liberty were given out, among them 2151 to Estonian citizens and 1064 to citizens of 17 other states. [...] The Highest Grade of Bravery was never awarded to anybody. The 2nd Grade was awarded to 29 men.

All divisions and classes of the Cross of Liberty, designed by Nikolai Triik (Walter 1998, 36; Kavaliauskas 1998, 57) have the same cross-shaped form, but the symbols at the center of the decorations are different for the divisions. The third division only has the letter E at its center (with a typography now remarkably similar to the Euro sign), while the first and second division combine this letter E with an armored hand holding a sword. It is the latter symbol that is an object of discursive struggle, which rendered it a floating signifier.

The Cross of Liberty, and in particular the version linked to heroism,²⁸ features prominently on the War of Independence Victory Column, at Freedom square in Tallinn. This 23,5-meter-high tower, consisting of 143 glass blocks, was designed by Rainer Sternfeld, Andri Laidre, Kadri Kiho, and Anto Savi, and inaugurated on 23 June 2009. Explicitly commemorating the victims of the War of Independence, the memorial is also seen to commemorate “all those who fought for the freedom and independence of Estonia.”²⁹ The (top of the) tower is modelled after the Estonian Cross of Liberty decoration, and thus incorporates its main symbol, the letter E, with the hand holding a sword. In Bellentani’s (2021, 96ff.) reception study of the memorial, the use of this iconography is shown to be met with resistance, as it “conveys meanings of might and control rather than freedom and mourning” (2021, 97). Moreover, “The majority of the Estonians suggested that Russophones may associate the iconography of the Victory Column with totalitarian aesthetics, being a military insignia used by Estonian soldiers fighting alongside the German army during WWII” (2021, 97).³⁰

27 See more at: <https://vp2006-2016.president.ee/en/estonia/decorations/decoration/119474/the-cross-of-liberty> and <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/12906303>.

28 To be exact: Division 2, Class I of the Cross of Liberty (Bellentani 2021, 80; Estonian Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Bellentani 2021, 84).

29 See more at: <https://db.esap.ee/object/t-0370> and <https://militaryheritagetourism.info/en/military/sites/view/335?0>.

30 Bellentani (2021, 97) points out that this concern did not materialize in their reception study.

But during the Second World War, also the Waffen-SS incorporated the symbol of the Cross of Liberty, on the collar patches of its uniforms, even though there was quite some diversity:

The Estonian Legion were [*sic*] authorized to blank right collar patches; some personal adopted the SS-runes; but special patches for the division later existed in three forms, at least two of which were widely used. (Williamson 2004, 37; see also Taylor 1986, 207–216)

The first version of these insignia was produced in Tartu, by the Surgical Instruments Factory, and had the letter E, with the armored hand holding a sword (although it had all the elements of the Cross of Liberty symbol, their placement was slightly different from the original Cross of Liberty). This collar patch was made from light metal, and sewn on the black collar patch (Taylor 1986, 211–212). This version was first given to the soldiers of the 45th regiment, in February 1944, and was later used by other units as well. The second version was issued by the Waffen-SS in June 1944, and had a machine-embroidered letter E with only a diagonally superimposed sword. According to Williamson (2004, 37), this second version was highly unpopular, and in the winter of 1944/45, a third version was designed, with the armored arm holding the sword, in combination with the letter E, copying the symbol of the Cross of Liberty decoration.

Some of the memorials include the symbol of the Cross of Liberty, articulated in this more radical-right-wing context. The clearest example is the Lihula memorial, which represents a Waffen-SS soldier, with the Cross of Liberty symbol clearly visible on the right collar patch of the uniform, as mentioned before. Less explicitly connected to the radical-right context, is the new memorial in Victory park in Pärnu. In November 2003, one year after the Lihula memorial was removed, a new memorial, designed by Kuno Raude, was placed in the park.³¹ The symbol of the Cross of Liberty, featured even more prominently here at the top of the black granite stone, together with the text: “To those who fought for the national independence of Estonia in World War II.” Both the location, in a park which was one of the key locations of this discursive-material struggle, and the text accompanying the symbol, tend to align the memorial with the radical-right wing agenda, and contribute to the

31 See more at: <https://militaryheritagetourism.info/en/military/sites/view/242?1&lang=en>; <https://epl.delfi.ee/artikkel/50969737/vabaduse-est-voidelnute-monument-jouab-parnusse>; <https://db.esap.ee/object/pa-0980>.

Figure 17. Elevation of a Floating Signifier.

Figure 18. *Iconoclastic Victory*.

floating of the signifier of the Cross of Liberty, being caught in the struggle of the articulation of the legitimate hero discourse.

Conclusion

The notion of the floating signifier is an important analytical instrument in discourse theory, as it allows us to capture how discourses strengthen their positions in hegemonic struggles, by integrating key signifiers into their always-particular constructions of our social worlds. As a concept, it contributes to a better understanding of signifiatory diversity. Moreover, the concept of the floating signifier also hints at the idea that not all struggles result in the establishment of hegemony, but are often simply ongoing, which also results in contingency at the level of the signifier itself. Arguably, when the concept of the floating signifier is confronted with discursive-material approaches – which shy away from establishing a hierarchy between the discursive and the material – the concept does not lose its strength. The acknowledgement of the significance of the material (as condensations of the discursive, with respect for material agency) allows us to analyze how

memorials, as discursive-material assemblages, which are crucial interventions in the construction of the Estonian self, can also float.

Our analysis demonstrates that discursive-material assemblages can play a diversity of roles in discursive struggles. Sometimes, they do not play a role at all, because their discursive affiliations are beyond contestation, as the meanings that they convey are too sacred to allow for contestation, at least at the present moment. In addition, memorials that are ignored or abandoned, left to decay, are not activated in discursive struggles, slowly removing particular discursive loads from them while being rendered historically insignificant. Even then, over time, a warehouse might again become more than a warehouse as the traces of its historical significance have not completely disappeared, given the problems to sell the building.

In other cases, discursive-material assemblages are at the heart of discursive struggles over their existence, not merely because of their own existence, but also because these assemblages are articulated in broader discourses. The 21st century struggles in the Estonian memorialscape are very much intersecting with the discourse of heroism, as they relate to the entitlement of being a legitimate hero. In war discourses, the hero is a nodal point of the construction of the Self, as the hero combines sacrifice, accomplishment and courage, and functions as an example for future generations. It is exactly its centrality that makes the hero an object of discursive-material struggle as well. In our research we can see that while the Waffen-SS soldiers, and more radical-right-wing actors, are still struggling to have their actions acknowledged as heroic, despite the resistance of Estonian mainstream (political) society, the Soviet soldiers, including the Heroes of the Soviet Union, lost the struggle for presence in the Estonian memorialscape. The removal of the Soviet memorials is thus also a performance of their exclusion from the discourse of heroism, and the attempted reduction of the range that the hero signifier can float. But even here, resistance, in the form of a public mourning of this loss, is still displayed as well, which prevents the complete cessation of the floating of the hero signifier (together with the continued presence of radical-right-wing articulations of the hero).

Thirdly, we can see how discursive-material memorial assemblages are also carriers of particular symbols, rendering them visible in public spaces, sometimes prominently towering over a city, sometimes placed in a centrally-located park, and other times confined to a private museum's garden. This

brings in the importance of space and materiality, where particular discursive articulations become condensed. In the Estonian case, the Cross of Liberty is a fascinating example of the material dimensions of the floating signifier, where the symbol not only gains material presence, but where the material context (and the entanglement of the discursive and material) is used to give particular meanings to this symbol, and thus to strengthen key discourses about the past, present, and future of Estonia. At the same time, the ongoing struggle over this floating signifier shows that – currently – there is no closure about what is the past, present, and future of Estonia. Even though we can celebrate this lack of total closure – as this generates spaces for human freedom and the political – this struggle also raises ethical concerns about how the darkest period in European 20th century history remains heavily contested.

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Short Biographies

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